

ASSESSING 3D MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES BASED ON DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

Guillaume Seon¹, Andrew Makeev¹, Julia Cline¹ and Erian Armanios¹

¹ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Texas at Arlington
500 West First Street, Arlington, Texas, 76019, U.S.A.

Email: seon@uta.edu, web page: <http://www.uta.edu/mae/AMSL>

Keywords: Digital image correlation, Stress-strain curves

ABSTRACT

Accurate and efficient full three-dimensional characterization of mechanical properties of composite materials, including stress-strain curves and strength characteristics, is essential for understanding complex deformation and failure mechanisms of composites and optimizing material qualification efforts. Non-contact full-field deformation measurement techniques, such as digital image correlation (DIC) allowing for assessment of all surface strain components on the entire specimen surface, enable simpler experimental setups and material specimen designs for more efficient and accurate material characterization.

This work presents some of the most recent advances by the authors in simultaneous assessment of lamina stress-strain curves in all principal material planes using a unidirectional small-plate torsion method. The method, which relies on the DIC to simultaneously measure deformation in the principal material planes and high-fidelity finite element model (FEM) based stress analysis to capture stress-strain relations in three dimensions, advances our ability to measure 3D material properties compared to the previous methodology developed by the authors that was able to use only small regions of the specimen surfaces in the material characterization.

An iterative FEM updating method is presented for assessment of the shear nonlinear stress-strain relationships of composite materials using the full-field strain data generated in small-plate torsion test specimens. The full-field strain optimization method enables simultaneous measurement of stress-strain relations in multiple material planes resulting in a significant reduction of the number of FEM iterations and allows for investigation of nonlinear material coupling among shear and tensile modes in the large strain regime. Results include the in-plane and two interlaminar stress-strain curves simultaneously captured for a practical carbon/epoxy tape material system. Dependency of in-plane shear response on axial and transverse stresses in the non-linear regime is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Accurate and efficient full three-dimensional characterization of mechanical properties of composite materials, including nonlinear shear stress-strain properties, is essential for understanding complex deformation and failure mechanisms of structures manufactured from highly anisotropic polymeric composite materials and optimizing material qualification efforts. Non-contact full-field deformation measurement techniques, such as digital image correlation (DIC) allowing for assessment of all surface strain components on the entire specimen surface, enable simpler experimental setups and material specimen designs for more efficient and accurate material characterization [1].

In pursuit of methods for measuring 3D mechanical properties of composites, the authors of this work have been developing techniques to fully capture the shear stress-strain curves in all principal material planes [4-6]. Most recent results, published in Composites Science and Technology [4], include the ability to characterize 2-3 plane interlaminar shear stress-strain curves, in addition to 1-3 plane interlaminar shear stress-strain curves, until material failure based on a small rectangular plate torsion (plate-twist) specimen using DIC measurement of deformation. For reference, 1 indicates the fiber direction; 2 the in-ply transverse direction; and 3 the laminate thickness direction. Earlier techniques including the short-beam shear (SBS) method, allowing for measuring most of the 3D stress-strain constitutive relations [5, 6], fell short of capturing nonlinear interlaminar shear properties

in the 2-3 principal material plane. The ability of unidirectional small-plate torsion specimens to simultaneously exhibit large shear strains in all principal material planes including 2-3 interlaminar shear in the non-linear regime, advanced the state-of-the-art of measuring 3D mechanical properties of composites in a single experiment [4]. The interlaminar shear stress-strain relations were obtained through coupling of DIC measurement based strain data with finite element model (FEM) based stresses, using a stress-update procedure where material properties in the FEM were updated until the change in the maximum FEM-based shear stress became negligible.

However, the previously developed techniques used only small regions of the test specimen surfaces, approaching line segments or points, in the material characterization. In order to take full advantage of the full-field measurement, all DIC surface strain data must be utilized. The methodology developed in this work represents a major advancement in our ability to measure 3D material properties by utilizing DIC measurement from the entire surface. In particular, this work extends the small-plate torsion method to utilizing the full-field measurement capability of DIC for a simultaneous assessment of the non-linear shear stress-strain constitutive relations in all three principal material planes. Full-field DIC-based surface strain measurements are also used in this work for investigation of material coupling between shear and axial and transverse modes.

Full-field measurements, allowing for identification of multiple material parameters in a single experimental setup and not subject to limitations of conventional material characterization requiring uniform strain, are attractive for assessment of material constitutive properties of composites [7]. Among strategies developed to solve the inverse problem of determining the material constitutive properties using the full field information, FEM updating (FEMU) method has been the most common approach and the virtual fields method (VFM) the most recent alternative. An extensive overview of inverse methods is given in Ref. [8]. Most of the existing work using inverse methods and full-field measurements for material characterization of composites has been focused on the identification of elastic properties such as orthotropic material constants or rigidities of laminated plates [9-11]. On the other hand, the in-plane and interlaminar shear behavior of polymeric composites is widely recognized to be nonlinear [12], and full characterization of the 3D shear stress-strain response is essential for understanding complex deformation and failure mechanisms in critical applications such as aircraft composite primary structures [1-3]. It is worth noting that full-field measurements coupled with the virtual fields method were used in Ref. [13] to determine the nonlinear shear behavior of a glass-epoxy composite based on double V-notched shear tests. However, only in-plane shear properties were identified and some restrictions inherent to the VFM approach, such as the complexity in choosing suitable virtual fields for arbitrary specimen configuration and test setup, could be mentioned.

In this work, an iterative FEMU method is presented for assessment of the shear nonlinear stress-strain relationships of composite materials using the full-field strain data generated in small-plate torsion test specimens. The new method is able to determine simultaneously the shear constitutive behavior in all three principal material planes and therefore significantly reduces the number of the FEM iterations compared to the previous methods handling one plane at a time. The basis of the inverse method is the minimization of the least square error between DIC-measured strains and FEM-predicted strains by fine-tuning the parameters of the material constitutive model. Full-field strain measurements on the three principal material planes (surfaces) of the small-plate torsion specimen include large strain gradients and allow for an efficient simultaneous determination of both linear and nonlinear material parameters, using only a limited number of DIC images generated during specimen loading. Results include the in-plane and two interlaminar stress-strain curves simultaneously captured for IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy material system. Dependency of in-plane shear response on axial and transverse stresses in the non-linear regime is discussed.

2 EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

To enable simultaneous assessment of the shear stress-strain response in the in-plane (1-2) and interlaminar (2-3 and 1-3) principal material planes, 11 small rectangular plate specimens were machined from a 26-ply 4.26 mm (0.168 in.) thick IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy unidirectional tape panel cured at 350 degrees F per prepreg manufacturer's specifications [15]. The specimen length and width

are 25.4 mm (1.00 in.). Figure 1 shows a small-plate torsion experimental setup with a test specimen under load and material orientation indicated.

Figure 1: A small-plate torsion experimental setup.

The small-plate specimens were placed in a custom test fixture with 6.35 mm (0.25-in.) diameter hemispherical supports; and loaded in a servo-hydraulic load frame at a constant 0.05 in/min crosshead displacement rate until failure. The support length was 17.8 mm (0.7 in.). The tests were conducted at 72° F room-temperature ambient conditions.

Figure 2: Three synchronized 16-megapixel stereo camera systems for simultaneous monitoring of surface strains in all principal material planes using the DIC technique.

DIC was used to assess the strain components on all principal material planes simultaneously. The reader is referred to Ref. [14] for a general description of the DIC technique; and to Refs. [4-6] for more specific details pertinent to this work. Three synchronized 16-megapixel stereo camera systems monitored strains in the 1-2, 2-3 and 1-3 principal material planes. Figure 2 shows a setup for simultaneously monitoring surface strain; and representative engineering shear strain components

measured right before specimen failure using the DIC technique. The strain analysis was performed in VIC-3D software [16] using a subset (data point) size of 35×35 pixels, corresponding to approximately 0.275 mm^2 for these particular tests. Data was obtained on 7 pixel centers, resulting in approximately 26,000 data points per load case.

Maximum in-plane and interlaminar shear strains greater than 5% are observed in both the 1-2 and 2-3 principal material planes, respectively, and greater than 3% in the 1-3 principal material plane before failure. This method allows for a comprehensive simultaneous assessment of shear strains for polymeric composites in all material planes.

3 INVERSE PROBLEM

The FEMU method used in this work for assessment of the material constitutive properties of composites, including nonlinear shear behavior, is based on a least squares optimization procedure. The objective error function $C(p)$ for the optimization problem is defined as the sum of the weighted squares of the differences between DIC-measured and FEM-computed strains and is given in matrix form in the following equation:

$$C(p) = (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{DIC} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{FEM}(p))^T \mathbf{W} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{DIC} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{FEM}(p)) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{p} represents the vector of unknown material parameters; $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{DIC}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{FEM}$ are the measured and computed strain vectors of order $M \times N$ with M the number of spatial grid points for evaluation of experimental and numerical strains and N the number of load steps at which digital images are generated. \mathbf{W} is the weight matrix such as:

$$\mathbf{W} = [W_{ij}]_{MN} \quad \text{with } W_{ij} = \begin{cases} w_{ii} & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The advantage of using strains in the expression of the objective function instead of using another quantity such as displacements is that the exact knowledge of the boundary conditions is less important and the sensitivity (or Jacobian) matrix used in the optimization procedure can be efficiently approximated without resorting to costly evaluation methods such as finite differences. It is worth noting that it might be necessary to consider a number N of load steps throughout the loading history of the specimen all the way to failure, in order to capture material non-linearities. For simplification purposes, only one strain component ε is used in the expression (1) of the objective function $C(p)$. For simultaneous assessment of multiple constitutive relations, all strain components involved in the stress-strain relationships need to be accounted for.

Ideally, the weighting factors in the objective function should be determined using the variance σ_j^2 in the experimental strain measurement at grid point j :

$$w_{jj} = \frac{1}{\sigma_j^2} \quad (3)$$

The confidence margin output parameter available in the DIC software Vic-3D is calculated from the covariance matrix of the correlation function [14] and is used in this work to estimate σ_j in equation (3). Weighted residuals used in the definition of the objective function allow reducing the sensitivity of the optimization algorithm to measurement noise, since the contribution of noisy data points with high variance is scaled down by the inverse of their variance.

No explicit relationship exists between FEM-computed strain components and the unknown material parameters; therefore the optimization problem has to be solved iteratively. A Levenberg-Marquardt (L-M) algorithm [17] is used to solve for the optimum material parameters that minimize the weighted least squares objective function. At iteration k , the material parameters are updated such as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^k &= \mathbf{p}^{k-1} + \Delta \mathbf{p}^k \\ \Delta \mathbf{p}^k &= [\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{J} + \lambda^k \text{diag}(\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{J})]^{-1} \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{W} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{DIC} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{FEM}(\mathbf{p}^k)) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{p}^k$, \mathbf{J} , and λ^k are respectively the vector of parameter updates, the Jacobian or sensitivity matrix and the L-M damping parameter at iteration k . The Jacobian matrix \mathbf{J} is defined as the matrix

of partial derivatives of the FEM-computed strain components with respect to the material parameters and is updated at each iteration k :

$$J = J^k = \left[\frac{\partial \varepsilon^{FEM}_i}{\partial p_j} \right]_{MN \times P} \quad (5)$$

with P indicating the number of the material parameters.

The L-M damping parameter is updated according to the approach presented in Ref. [18]. The L-M iterative procedure is stopped when the maximum normalized error in parameter update is less than a user-defined threshold ε :

$$\max \left| \frac{\Delta p_i}{p_i} \right| \leq \varepsilon \text{ for } i = 1..P \quad (6)$$

4 NUMERICAL MODEL

A three-dimensional FEM was developed for stress calculation in the small-plate torsion specimens, using commercial finite element modeling software ABAQUS [19]. Figure 3 shows a typical finite element mesh including approximately 75,000 first-order three-dimensional incompatible mode solid elements (C3D8I). Incompatible mode elements are well suited for the torsion/bending problem considered in this work, since the additional incompatible deformation modes, added to the element formulation, eliminate parasitic shear stresses and stiffening usually found in the bending response of regular first-order elements [19]. The supports are assumed to be rigid and are modeled as rigid analytical spherical surfaces. Frictionless contact conditions are assigned between the specimen surfaces and the support points. A surface-to-surface contact formulation is selected in ABAQUS in order to avoid local indentation stresses at contact points. The FEM accounts for geometric nonlinearity; and the material constitutive model for IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy, including shear nonlinearity, is implemented via a user subroutine UMAT.

A mesh refinement sensitivity study was performed to ensure that proper stress convergence is achieved. It is worth noting that at least 16 elements in the thickness direction were required to ensure convergence of the maximum shear stress and correctly capture strong stress gradients. The final converged finite element model had approximately 1,150,000 degrees of freedom.

Figure 3: A three-dimensional finite element model of a unidirectional small-plate torsion specimen

The following Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios are utilized [6] for IM7/8552: $E_{11} = 157$ GPa; $E_{22} = E_{33} = 8.96$ GPa; $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.32$; and $\nu_{23} = 0.5$. Log-linear Ramberg-Osgood [20] type equations are used to characterize the shear stress-strain nonlinearity with three material parameters (G, K, n) that are determined in this work through the full-field optimization procedure.

$$\gamma = \frac{\tau}{G} + \left(\frac{\tau}{K} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (7)$$

where γ is shear strain, τ is shear stress, G is the linear shear modulus, and K, n are the secant-intercept modulus and the exponent material constants characterizing shear nonlinearity in the composite material.

The Jacobian matrix is computed for a total of 9 material parameters p_i corresponding to the Ramberg-Osgood (G, K, n) parameters in all three principal material planes. Analytical approximations of the sensitivities terms in the Jacobian matrix are obtained by using expression (5) in equation (7) and assuming that the variation of stress with respect to the material parameters is negligible. Such approximation was verified by computing the Jacobian matrix using the finite differences technique. The stress-strain relations obtained by finite differences for a typical specimen were in close agreement with the results based on the analytical approximation of the sensitivities. However, it is worth noting that nine additional FEM analyses at each iteration of the optimization procedure are required to compute the Jacobian matrix in the finite differences method. No additional costly FEM calculation is needed with the analytical approximation of the Jacobian matrix, since sensitivities are computed from the same FEM analysis used for evaluation of the objective function.

Nonlinear material properties generated based on short-beam tests [6] are used to define the initial shear material behavior in the 1-2 and 1-3 principal material planes: $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.08$ GPa, $K_{12} = K_{13} = 0.249$ GPa and $n_{12} = n_{13} = 0.248$. Transverse isotropy has been assumed for the initial approximation of the shear modulus in the 2-3 principal material plane: $G_{23} = E_{22}/(2*(1+\nu_{23})) = 2.99$ GPa. The initial approximation for the 2-3 plane nonlinear material shear properties is $K_{23} = K_{13} = 0.249$ GPa; and $n_{23} = n_{13} = 0.248$.

4 RESULTS

The full-field strain L-M optimization method presented in the previous section has been used to extract the parameters in the Ramberg-Osgood equations for the shear stress-strain relations for IM7/8552 composite material using DIC full-field shear strain measurements in the three principal material planes of the small-plate torsion specimen. A 0.1% maximum relative change in parameter update was used as a stopping criterion for the iterative L-M procedure, as defined in expression (6). Four or five iterations are typically required to establish convergence of the optimization model. The Python scripting capability of Abaqus CAE is used for implementation of the L-M algorithm.

DIC-measured and FEM-computed strains values must be evaluated at the same spatial location for computation of the objective function and the Jacobian matrix used in the L-M algorithm. A set of FEM nodes on each material plane for surface strain measurements has been used for interpolation of element strain results and DIC strain data. Specimen edges are excluded from the analysis, as DIC measurements are typically less accurate at specimen boundaries. The observation windows containing the FEM nodes for interpolation of full-field strain data are illustrated in Figure 4. Element C^0 shape functions are used for interpolation of FEM strains at the nodes. The natural neighbour interpolation method implemented in Python function *griddata* of module *SciPy* is used for interpolation of the DIC strains on the nodes of the observation windows.

Figure 4: Observation windows showing typical interpolated nodal shear strain data obtained from DIC full-field strain measurements in the (a) 1-2 principal material plane; (b) 1-3 plane; and (c) 2-3 plane.

Figure 5 shows the values of the normalized objective function (a), the total RMS normalized error in maximum shear strain between DIC-measured and FEM-computed strains (b) and the maximum error in parameter update (c) at each iteration of the full-field optimization for a typical specimen. The normalized objective function is defined as the ratio of the objective function given in (1) at the

current iteration by the objective function at the first iteration. The RMS normalized error in maximum shear strain is computed as:

$$\varepsilon_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3N} \sum_{i=1}^{3N} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{max_i}^{DIC} - \varepsilon_{max_i}^{FEM}}{\varepsilon_{max_i}^{DIC}} \right)^2} \quad (8)$$

where ε_{max_i} are the maximum shear strain components on the three principal material planes for the N numbers of loading steps. The maximum error in parameter update is defined in expression (9).

Figure 5: (a) Normalized objective function; (b) maximum normalized strain error; and (c) maximum error in parameter update at each iteration of the full-field L-M optimization procedure for a typical small-plate torsion specimen.

A rapid decrease of the objective error function, maximum RMS strain error, and the update in parameters has been demonstrated for the first iterations. It is worth noting that the total RMS maximum strain error is reduced from 7% for the initial approximation of the material parameters, to less than 2.5% for the converged constitutive properties.

Convergence of the stress-strain curves with the number of load steps N at which DIC images are generated and used for full-field strain optimization was investigated. Figure 6 shows the RMS normalized error in stress values for the stress-strain curves using different numbers of load steps equally spaced throughout the loading history, compared to the converged response obtained using 20 load steps. It is worth noting that the maximum RMS error is only 2.7% when a single DIC image (corresponding to the maximum load) is used per plane and a rapid convergence is observed. This is related to the fact that a single full-field DIC strain measurement at maximum load includes strain values spanning linear to fully non-linear range, as shown on Figure 2, which allows for simultaneous extraction of linear and nonlinear material parameters. Computing time until convergence of the inverse procedure using 20 DIC images is approximately 120 minutes using 12 processors for the FEM solver; whereas only 15 minutes are required when one DIC full-field measurement is used. It is worth noting that the previous method developed by the authors in Ref. [4] was based on the measurement of the maximum shear strain only and therefore required a significant number of DIC measurements for complete assessment of the nonlinear shear stress-strain material response.

Figure 6: Convergence of the nonlinear shear stress-strain relations in the three principal material planes with the number of load steps used in the full-field optimization.

The robustness of the proposed method was verified by using different initial approximations of the non-linear shear properties. Figure 7 shows the converged stress-strain curves obtained for a typical specimen starting from two different initial approximations A and B of the material parameters, as illustrated. Convergence is obtained after 5 iterations for approximation A and 6 iterations for approximation B. The converged models for the non-linear behavior in the three material planes obtained from both initial approximations are in very good agreement and also closely match the converged solution obtained from the SBS initial properties. It is worth noting that the maximum RMS normalized error in stress values between the two converged solutions and with the converged model from the SBS initial approximation is less than 1.8% for the three planes.

Figure 7: Converged shear-stress strain curves obtained from two different initial approximations A and B in (a) 1-2 principal material plane; (b) 1-3 plane; and (c) 2-3 plane. For reference, approximation A uses $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.07$ GPa, $G_{23} = 2.39$ GPa, $K_{12} = K_{13} = K_{23} = 0.224$ GPa, and $n_{12} = n_{13} = n_{23} = 0.248$. Approximation B uses $G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.10$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.58$ GPa, $K_{12} = K_{13} = K_{23} = 0.274$ GPa, and $n_{12} = n_{13} = n_{23} = 0.248$.

Converged shear stress-strain curves obtained for the eleven IM7/8552 specimens are presented in Figure 8 and compared with the initial approximation of the shear response. Thirteen DIC images taken at load steps equally spaced throughout the loading history were used for extraction of the material properties. Non-linear shear properties obtained for all specimens are summarized in Table 1. Table 1 also lists the average value of the parameters with the associated coefficient of variation (COV) and the RMS error between DIC and FEM strains at the maximum shear strain location for all planes. It is worth noting that scatter in the log-linear parameters G , K and n is small for the three principal planes, as indicated by lower than 5.2% COV, with the maximum variability in the G_{13} shear modulus. Close agreement between FEM-strains for the converged solution and DIC-strains is

demonstrated by lower than 3.2% total RMS error for the maximum shear strains in each material plane.

Figure 8: Initial approximation, individual stress-strain curves and average response for the 11 IM7/8552 specimens in (a) 1-2 principal material plane; (b) 1-3 plane; and (c) 2-3 plane.

Specimens	G_{12} , GPa	K_{12} , MPa	n_{12}	G_{13} , GPa	K_{13} , MPa	n_{13}	G_{23} , GPa	K_{23} , MPa	n_{23}	Max strain error
1	5.15	237	0.255	4.72	254	0.246	2.90	248	0.247	2.2%
2	5.20	236	0.257	4.45	248	0.255	2.85	251	0.244	2.4%
3	5.05	234	0.258	4.84	246	0.253	2.92	244	0.249	2.0%
4	5.45	236	0.255	4.56	252	0.250	2.72	253	0.244	3.2%
5	5.23	236	0.256	4.40	246	0.255	2.92	248	0.247	1.5%
6	5.33	235	0.256	4.93	252	0.249	2.85	251	0.246	3.0%
7	5.02	235	0.258	4.48	247	0.251	2.89	249	0.244	2.1%
8	5.06	236	0.257	4.42	247	0.254	2.91	252	0.243	2.2%
9	4.94	241	0.254	4.38	253	0.248	2.96	254	0.240	2.6%
10	5.05	235	0.258	4.41	247	0.255	2.94	249	0.245	2.2%
11	5.03	237	0.257	4.45	246	0.254	2.93	250	0.244	2.2%
AVG	5.13	237	0.256	4.59	249	0.251	2.90	250	0.245	
COV	2.9%	1.7%	1.1%	5.2%	1.2%	1.2%	2.3%	1.1%	1.1%	

Table 1: Non-linear shear properties for the small-plate torsion specimens.

It is found that the linear portion of the shear stress-strain response in the 1-2 plane agrees well with the initial approximation from SBS results, with less than 1% error on the average shear modulus value. As strains become larger, the converged small-plate torsion stress-strain response deviates from SBS results in the non-linear regime, with about 6.5% of relative error in average shear stress at maximum strains. The deviation of the non-linear shear response in the non-linear regime for the 1-2 principal material plane might be due to the effects of material coupling in the nonlinear stress-strain regime, as discussed later. Reasonable agreement is found between the SBS approximation and the shear stress-strain curve obtained from the full-field optimization method for the 1-3 interlaminar plane, with less than 5% of relative stress error at maximum strain between the average response and the SBS approximation. The error mostly comes from the shear modulus G_{13} , with an average modulus about 9.6% lower than the results from SBS. It is worth noting that SBS and small plate-torsion specimens were fabricated years apart by different manufacturers from different batches of prepreg. Therefore, the difference in the SBS results could be attributed to the effects of the material and process variabilities. The average converged shear stress-strain curve obtained for the 2-3 plane closely matches the initial approximation and exhibits low scatter. This result suggests that the non-linear shear stress-strain response in the 2-3 plane can be accurately assessed by using the transverse isotropy approximation for the shear modulus, and the K and n parameters obtained from characterization of the shear nonlinear behavior in the 1-3 plane.

5 MATERIAL COUPLING

Multi-axial stress distribution on the top surface of the small-plate torsion specimen is due to the combination of twist and bending deformation. Such distribution allows for investigation of material coupling among shear and extension modes in the non-linear regime by using the full-field strain measurement capability of the DIC technique and FEM-based stress calculation.

Typical in-plane shear, and axial and transverse normal stress fields on the observation window of the 1-2 principal material plane of the small-plate torsion specimens at maximum load before failure (around 2400 N) are shown in Figure 9. As illustrated, high transverse and axial normal stress gradients due to bending are observed in the region corresponding to the support contact surface on the opposite side. In-plane shear stress distribution is uniform over most of the specimen surface and rapidly reaches the non-linear regime, around 30% of the specimen failure load.

It is worth noting that in the two other principal material planes (1-3 and 2-3 planes), axial and transverse stresses are negligible in regions with high shear stress. Therefore, investigation of material coupling in the shear response is limited to the 1-2 principal material for the test configuration considered in this work.

Figure 9: Stress distribution in the observation window of the 1-2 principal material plane of the small-plate torsion test specimens for (a) σ_{12} ; (b) σ_{11} ; and (c) σ_{22} stresses at maximum load before failure

In Figure 10, FEM-based in-plane shear stress data for each node in the observation window is plotted versus the corresponding DIC-interpolated strain data for a typical specimen after full-field optimization of the shear material properties in all material planes. The stress-strain data points are colored based on the value of the axial and transverse stress component in the top and bottom charts of Figure 10, respectively. For illustration purposes, data from only five DIC images taken throughout the loading history are presented. The shear stress-strain curve obtained from the full-field strain optimization model in the 1-2 plane is also plotted. It is worth noting that FEM-based stress analysis does not include extension-shear coupling.

Scatter in the stress-strain data plotted in Figure 10 is expected due to strain measurement errors. A total RMS error of 8.6% is found by comparing the stress-strain data from experimental strain measurement to the converged stress-strain curved of the optimization model. However, it is worth noting that the scatter in shear strain is unlikely to be due to random measurement noise alone, as it appears to be strongly spatially correlated with the axial stress distribution. It is shown that in areas with high tensile axial stresses, DIC-measured shear strains in the non-linear regime are lower than expected from the uncoupled model. Such trend suggests the presence of material coupling among in-plane shear strain response and axial normal tensile stresses. On the other hand, it is shown in Figure 10 that data points corresponding to high transverse normal tensile stress locations overlay the shear stress-strain response of data points with negligible transverse stresses. Therefore, it is possible that no dependency exists between the in-plane shear strain response and transverse normal tensile stresses.

Figure 10: Color plots of the in-plane shear stress-strain data obtained from FEM-calculated stresses and DIC-measured strains using the axial (top) and transverse (bottom) normal stress distribution in the observation window for the 1-2 principal material plane.

9 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A new method taking the full advantage of the full-field measurement capability of DIC for a simultaneous assessment of non-linear shear stress-strain relations for composites in all three principal material planes has been presented in this work. The method, which employs a small rectangular plate torsion specimen, advances our ability to measure 3D material properties compared to the previous methodology that was able to use only small regions of the specimen surfaces approaching line segments or points. The resulting material stress-strain constitutive models are relying on the DIC data including the in-plane and out-of-plane strain components; and on iterative FEM-based stress calculation. Results include the in-plane and two interlaminar stress-strain curves simultaneously captured for a practical IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy tape system.

Close agreement was found between results obtained with the full-field optimization method and data generated from SBS tests in the 1-3 interlaminar plane; and a practical approximation suitable for evaluation of the non-linear shear properties in the 2-3 principal material plane was proposed. Investigation of material coupling in the 1-2 principal material plane suggested strong evidence of dependency of in-plane shear strain response and axial normal stresses. The slight deviation found between full-field strain optimization results and SBS reference data in the 1-2 principal material plane might be explained if these material couplings are accounted for. Further verifications and identification of the coupling properties will be the subject of future work by the authors.

Complexity of the three-dimensional deformation exhibited by the small-plate torsion specimens; and the ability of the method to capture multiple basic nonlinear matrix-dominated stress-strain properties in a single experiment advocate for assessing accurate 3D stress-strain relations for composites and verifying various simplifying assumptions. The method has a strong potential for becoming a platform for deriving basic nonlinear stress-strain material constitutive properties in three dimensions using a single specimen configuration and employing synchronized full-field strain measurement in three principal material planes.

After further development, not only material properties for specific material systems but also the material model formulation itself, including material couplings in the non-linear regime, can potentially be derived using an iterative updating process involving FEM based simulations and DIC measurements. Such methodology would enable accurate and efficient full three-dimensional characterization of nonlinear material properties of composites, using the minimum number of experiments, reducing the amount of material testing to understand complex properties governing deformation and failure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is sponsored by the US Army and Navy Vertical Lift Research Center of Excellence (VLRCE). Such support is gratefully acknowledged. The authors also thank Mr. Edward Lee at Bell Helicopter Textron and Mr. Steven Grohman at Triumph for manufacturing the test specimens.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.G. Davila, P.P. Camanho, and C.A. Rose, Failure criteria for FRP laminates. *J. Comp. Mat.*, **39**(4), 2005, pp. 323-345.
- [2] A. Makeev A and Y. Nikishkov, Fatigue life assessment for composite structure, *ICAF 2011 Structural Integrity Influence of Efficiency and Green Imperatives*, J. Komorowski, Editor, Springer, 2011, pp. 119-135.
- [3] Y. Nikishkov, A. Makeev and G. Seon, Progressive fatigue damage simulation method for composites, *Int. J. Fatigue*, **48**, 2013, pp. 266-279.
- [4] A. Makeev, G. Seon, J. Cline, and B. Shonkwiler, In quest of methods for measuring 3D mechanical properties of composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **100**, 2014, pp. 105-112.
- [5] A. Makeev, Y. He, P. Carpentier and B. Shonkwiler, A method for measurement of multiple constitutive properties for composite materials, *Compos: Part A*, **43**(12), 2012, pp. 2199–2210.
- [6] A. Makeev, Y. He and H. Schreier, Short-beam shear method for assessment of stress-strain curves for fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composite materials, *Strain*, **49**, 2013, pp. 440-450.
- [7] M. Grediac, The use of full-field measurement methods in composite material characterization: interest and limitations, *Compos: Part A*, **35**(7), 2004, pp. 751-761
- [8] S. Avril et al, Overview of identification methods of mechanical parameters based on full-field measurements, *Exp. Mech*, **48**, 2008, pp. 381-402.
- [9] K. Genovese, L. Lamberti and C. Pappalettere, A new hybrid technique for in-plane characterization of orthotropic materials, *Exp. Mech*, **44**(6), 2004, pp. 584-592.
- [10] J. Molimard, R. Le Riche, A. Vautrin, and J.R. Lee, Identification of the four orthotropic plate stiffnesses using a single open-hole tensile test, *Exp. Mech.*, **45**(5), 2005, pp. 404-411.
- [11] D. Lecompte, A. Smits, H. Sol, J. Vantomme and D. Van Hemelrijck, Mixed numerical–experimental technique for orthotropic parameter identification using biaxial tensile tests on cruciform specimens, *Inter. J of Solids & Struct.*, **44**(5), 2007, pp. 1643-1656.
- [12] G. Zhou, E. R. Green and C. Morrison, In-plane and interlaminar shear properties of carbon/epoxy laminates, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **55**(2), 1995, pp. 187-193.
- [13] H. Chalal et al, Experimental identification of a nonlinear model for composites using the grid technique coupled to the virtual fields method, *Compos: Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 315-325.

- [14] M. A. Sutton, J.J. Orteu and H. Schreier, Image correlation for shape, motion and deformation measurements, New York: Springer, 2009.
- [15] http://www.hexcel.com/Resources/DataSheets/Prepreg-Data-Sheets/8552_us.pdf
- [16] VIC3D-7. <http://www.correlatedsolutions.com>
- [17] D.W. Marquardt, An algorithm for least-squares estimation of nonlinear parameters, *J. of Soc. for Indust. & Appl. Maths*, **11**(2), 1963, pp. 431-441.
- [18] H. B. Nielsen, Damping Parameter in Marquardt's Method, *Informatics and Mathematical Modelling*, Technical University of Denmark, DTU, 1999.
- [19] ABAQUS® version 6.12 analysis user's manual. Providence: Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012.
- [20] W. A. Ramberg and W. R. Osgood, Description of stress–strain curves by three parameters, *National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics*, Technical Note No. 902, 1943.